

Is Artificial intelligence really pivotal or not for human potential?

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Annotation. Artificial intelligence refers to the capability of technology to submit tasks that typically require human intelligence. Its significant functions can be problem-solving, learning, perception and language understanding. This system is created to analyze vast amount of statistics, special details, realize patterns, make decisions about the given data. The main purpose of the study is to check how impact Artificial intelligence for learners' studying on their curriculum platform or period of preparing kind of international exams. This problem relies on scientific approach with rational argument. The research delves into utilizing Artificial intelligence among youngs by practitioners. The results of this study explore that some programs can help students to assess themselves.

Key words: Artificial intelligence, practitioners, speciality, influence, learning process, progress.

Аннотация. Искусственный интеллект — это способность технологии выполнять задачи, которые обычно требуют человеческого интеллекта. Его важными функциями могут быть решение проблем, обучение, восприятие и понимание языка. Эта система создана для анализа огромного количества статистики, особых деталей, выявления закономерностей, принятия решений на основе имеющихся данных. Основная цель исследования — проверить, как искусственный интеллект повлияет на обучение учащихся на их учебной платформе или на период подготовки к международным экзаменам. Эта проблема опирается на научный подход с рациональной аргументацией. Исследование посвящено использованию практикующими искусственного интеллекта среди молодежи. Результаты этого исследования показывают, что

некоторые программы могут помочь учащимся оценивать себе самостоятельно.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, практики, специальность, влияние, процесс обучения, прогресс.

Annotatsiya. Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyaning odatda inson aqlini talab qiladigan vazifalarni topshirish qobiliyatini anglatadi. Uning muhim vazifalari muammolarni hal qilish, o'rganish, idrok etish va tilni tushunish bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu tizim katta miqdordagi statistik ma'lumotlarni, maxsus tafsilotlarni tahlil qilish, tamoyillarini tushunish, berilgan ma'lumotlar bo'yicha qaror qabul qilish uchun yaratilgan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi – sun'iy intellektning o'quvchilarning o'quv platformalarida yoki xalqaro imtihonlarga tayyorgarlik ko'rish davrida o'qishlariga qanday ta'sir qilishini tekshirish. Bu muammo asosli dalillar bilan ilmiy yondashuvga tayanadi. Tadqiqot amaliyotchilar tomonidan yoshlar o'rtasida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishga qaratilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ba'zi dasturlar talabalarga o'zlarini baholashga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt, amaliyotchilar, mutaxassislik, ta'sir, o'quv jarayoni, taraqqiyot.

Introduction

Utilizing artificial intelligence in education has gained significant attention in recent years. A systematic review covering 138 articles from 2016 to 2022 highlights a surge in AI applications in higher education, particularly in language learning and student assessment. Research indicates that over 70% of undergraduate students use AI tools for understanding concepts, literature research, and problem-solving . It explores the evolution of AI technologies, their applications in personalized learning, intelligent tutoring systems, and adaptive learning environments. The authors highlight both the potential benefits and challenges, including ethical concerns and the need for effective integration strategies to enhance educational outcomes. This work contributes to understanding how AI can revolutionize teaching and learning practices in contemporary education[1].

Information technologies, particularly artificial intelligence AI, are revolutionizing modern education. AI algorithms and educational robots are now integral to learning management and training systems, providing support for a wide array of teaching and learning activities. Numerous applications of AI in education have emerged. For example, Khan Academy offers Khanmigo, an AI tutor harnessing GPT-4 capabilities, delivering personalized learning support and

intelligent feedback across various subjects, including mathematics, programming, and language learning. Similarly, Duolingo, a language learning platform, uses sophisticated AI systems to improve learner experiences[2].

Today we live in 21st century which is recognized as a global technology period. Meanwhile, life is getting somehow simplified day by day according to modernization. The main reason is that existence of milestone for everything. And also, mankind needn't overthink or worry about to do anything too much. Thanks to, Artificial intelligence learners hardly face to the issue to create any idea. However, some people possess negative opinions about Artificial intelligence. The conclusion of the research can put stress to the pros and cons the influence of Artificial intelligence at the school, lyceum, college or University levels in any speciality can be productive for both teaching and learning process or it prevents progress and it seldom lets students to enhance themselves as a thought-provoking learner. According to their thoughts that Artificial intelligence may prevent learners to evolve as an independent individual who has own rational and concrete ideas. As a consequence, students get constantly used to questing something special from AI and they can be dependent to it instead of broadening their horizon through reading paper- based books, handouts. Briefly, despite of working on themselves, focusing on their thinking capability, learners tend to utilize Artificial intelligence as a ready material. Although some people find slight drawbacks related to utilizing artificial intelligence, there are plenty of benefits for learners who are determined to pass with flying colours. In this research paper, advantages and disadvantages of artificial intelligence will be conducted with breakthrough discussion.

Research Methodology

Initially, if young individuals never make use of their minds, they simply become servants of artificial intelligence. It sounds extremely horrible, doesn't it?

Several researchers have expressed negative opinions about using artificial intelligence AI in studies:

Andrew Gillen cautioned that AI lacks the human perspective necessary for qualitative research, emphasizing the importance of a researcher's positionality in promoting trust in findings[3].

Bernard Marr highlighted concerns about AI's potential to perpetuate biases and diminish critical thinking skills, warning against overreliance on AI systems[4].

Shojaei pointed out that AI can lead to dehumanization and erosion of genuine human connections, stressing the need for ethical standards in AI deployment.

Perhaps, they may have lack of idea how to utilize correctly from artificial intelligence. Mostly, students tend to copying others' all ideas as their own opinion without any citation. Some learners just write and quest wanted resources to special programs which are counted above by some practitioners and they submit given resources as a personalized by themselves. They may not realize that it can be type of crime, shame to plagiarize someone's the whole ideas, expressions.

Result and discussion

Despite the arguments mentioned above, Artificial intelligence brings about considerable advantages. By integrating young students into educational practices, particularly to enhance their learning experiences, many practitioners have shared innovative ideas and strategies for utilizing AI in education. Here are some notable contributions:

Sabba Quidwai is CEO of Designing Schools: Quidwai emphasizes the importance of balancing human creativity with AI assistance. She advocates for using tools like ChatGPT and Canva to facilitate collaborative idea generation in classrooms[5]. By making classroom conversations visible through digital whiteboards, educators can enhance brainstorming sessions, ensuring that while AI organizes ideas, the ultimate decision-making remains human-driven.

Aileen Wallace is High School Teacher: Wallace utilizes the AI learning platform Curipod to engage quieter students. The platform allows students to participate anonymously, which helps create a safe environment free from judgment. Features like moderation and voting on ideas foster collaboration and build confidence among students, encouraging them to share their thoughts more freely.

Matthew Wemyss: Wemyss focuses on resource planning and professional development through AI tools like ChatGPT and Office 365's Copilot. His approach highlights how AI can streamline administrative tasks, allowing educators to dedicate more time to teaching and supporting students.

Eric Curts is EdTech Specialist: Curts presented on using the Chrome extension Brisk Teaching, which streamlines teaching by automating routine tasks. This enables teachers to focus more on instructional quality rather than administrative burdens.

Jason Gulya is English Professor: Gulya explores how AI can enhance literature studies by providing personalized learning experiences. He advocates for using AI to tailor reading materials and assignments to individual student interests and abilities, thus promoting deeper engagement with the content[6].

All of them could convey clearly their ideas regarding Artificial intelligence. According to my perspective opinion, I would admit only benefits of using Artificial intelligence. Initially, it can be simply accessible to provide quality educational resources for all students, regardless of their location, their economic status. And also, students can check their mistakes, assess their own works and identify their concrete level. Another intriguing point is that, Artificial intelligence can facilitate to immerse learning through productive programs such as Chatgpt, Perplexity and it can engage students to complex subjects. Additionally, students can create perfect, well designed presentations through Canva and perform their work with alluring pictures to their teachers and audience. This picture can be perfect example to clarify this app's structure. It can be helpful both students and teachers to make presentations creatively.

By automating routine tasks, AI help students to schedule their time efficiently and it can prevent looking screens a lot and using Incredibly from social media.

One more notable point is that learners can embark on developing intensively their speaking level by downloading several programs which a thing or two described above in these pictures, like Elsa speak, Duolingo, woodpecker language learning, Hello talk, paradot and so on.

Conclusion

All in all, the results of this study reveal that artificial intelligence serves to upsurge mankind, instead of ruining individuals' life.

Today human live in modern life. Revolution, milestone can be occurred on the back of highly-gifted people's efforts. As it is said: "Future depends on youngsters' hand". That's why learners must be able to use from amenities for their development. And in that case artificial intelligence can spark learners to engage even hard classes and to evolve their communication skills. Artificial intelligence is productive aid for both teachers and students. To clarify this, teachers can make compelling presentations to grab students' attention in any topic. Furthermore, studies suggest that AI can enhance learning experiences by providing personalized feedback and supporting diverse learning styles. Learners can check their essays, analyze their mistakes and realize deep understanding as an independent learner.

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